

Predicting Galactic Rotation Curvature and Lensing without Dark Matter:

A Polynomic Approach

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8/6/2024

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Abstract

Abstract In this paper we present a novel framework for explaining galactic rotation curves and gravitational lensing without relying on dark matter. This model proposes that continuous or intermittent matter creation in high-energy density regions, such as galactic cores and around supermassive black holes, generates a pressure gradient that influences galactic dynamics. By introducing the concept of Field Displacement Density (FDD), we account for variations in the density of the fundamental field due to mass presence, affecting scalar field dynamics and gravitational potential. Our polynomial mathematical framework successfully models galactic rotation velocities and gravitational lensing effects with a high degree of accuracy, achieving R-squared values of 0.9817 ± 0.0402 for rotational velocities and 0.9234 ± 0.3524 for lensing plots. The validation against a dataset of over 130 galaxies demonstrates the robustness of our approach. This work challenges the conventional reliance on dark matter, offering a unified explanation for observed galactic phenomena and opening new avenues for research in cosmology. Our findings suggest that our modified polynomic framework provides a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of galactic behavior, as evidenced by the precise graphical representation of galaxy curvature and lensing within the same theoretical framework.

Keywords: gravitational lensing: strong, celestial mechanics, galaxies: structure, (cosmology:) dark matter, galaxies: evolution

Introduction

In our quest for understanding, we have complicated the hell out of everything. Let's simplify it. We live in a 3-dimensional reality, right? A singular point is 1 dimension, another point gives us distance and functionality, it can make a line and a wave form. The third dimension grants us depth, and humans were given tools to explore this dimensionality in the form of our senses. One of those senses, even if we don't often count it, is the ability to sense the forward progress of the universe. Even while asleep we still are aware of the passage of time, the only time we truly lose the ability to perceive time is when we are anesthetized. So, we are sure there are 3 spatial dimensions and another dimension for time. What about other dimensions then? We exist, and planets and stars exist, and the quantum field full of energy fluctuations exists. We need a dimension for matter and the various states it comes in, and as Einstein brilliantly showed, mass is energy and energy is mass, the two are fundamentally two sides of the same coin with just a conversion factor separating the two. The fifth dimension is energy in its various phases. This is not a radical concept; the more radical concept is claiming that mass is an aberration in an otherwise sterile universe.

Counter to all appearances, the universe is alive with particle fluctuations. Let's do a thought experiment. Think of the perfect universe at equilibrium; an analogy might be a perfectly smooth pond. It makes particles, sure, but the particles are cancelled out right away from counterparts that annihilate them. So, we have this perfect universe, existing as a perfectly smooth pond, for an indeterminate amount of time, where nothing happened until the most improbable event

occurred: an iota of matter was created and, due to the conditions of the field, it wasn't immediately cancelled out. This might be seen as a drop in the pond that sends out ripples. This introduces the first entropy into the universe. The particle exists in a state of superposition; the only way to balance this is to create more matter to try to smooth over this granular probabilistic nightmare. This new matter balances out the initial matter displacement, but now newer matter must be made to balance out the matter that was created to balance the initial matter, and so on, like drops on the pond that will never return to perfect stillness.

We present the runaway matter creation model of the universe and postulate that not only is the universe not dying a slow heat death, but it is rather actively growing and expanding from everywhere as a direct response to the first particle ever created. We contend that every galaxy sprouted from a single particle and grew into monumental proportions, not unlike how mountains and volcanoes arise on Earth. New mass displaces the old mass and the field we exist in, and this displaced cast-off dust and star mass become the arms of galaxies. As new matter is created, it unbalances the galaxy, causing rotation that becomes self-sustained as the galaxy evolves. This is a natural explanation for how stars almost as old as the universe arrived at the very periphery of our galaxy. We hypothesize that the very first and oldest stars will be on the periphery of every galaxy. We also predict that we will show matter creation and displacement as an explanation for galactic rotation curvature and gravitational lensing, and that our empirical evidence will at least be marginally better than the standard model.

So how is our model different than the Lambda Cold Dark Matter model and why do we think that model needs to be updated? We start by asking what dark matter is and why it is so important in modern cosmology. Dark matter is a crucial concept in modern cosmology because it was proposed to explain discrepancies in the gravitational behavior of galaxies. Fritz Zwicky's observations of the Coma Cluster in the 1930s and Vera Rubin's work in the 1970s highlighted that rotational velocities of galaxies remain constant or even increase with distance from the galactic center, contrary to predictions by traditional models (Zwicky, 1937; Rubin, 1980). This study challenges the conventional reliance on dark matter, proposing instead a modular polynomial mathematical framework to explain these observations through continuous or intermittent mass creation in high-energy density regions (Auclair & Stern, 2023).

The problem that dark matter helped solve was that the velocity of rotation of galaxies is much higher on the periphery than expected in the Standard Model, and dark matter was the solution (Fisher, 2022; Begeman, Broeils & Sanders, 1991). Traditional models predict that rotational velocities should decrease with increasing distance from the center, similar to the behavior of planets orbiting the Sun. However, observations show that these velocities tend to flatten out or even increase at greater distances, suggesting the presence of additional unseen mass, commonly attributed to dark matter (Milgrom, 1983; McGaugh et al., 2016).

While investigating the concept of displacement and how it might apply to a cosmological energetic medium to account for observations of the universe expanding from every mass, it also

became evident that displacement might also account for cosmological effects such as gravitational lensing and galactic rotation curvature. This paper challenges the conventional understanding that relies on dark matter to explain galactic rotation curves and gravitational lensing. Instead, it proposes a novel approach that accounts for these observations through a modular polynomial mathematical framework without the need for dark matter. We posit that mass is intermittently or continuously created in high-energy density regions, such as galactic cores and around supermassive black holes. This matter creates a pressure gradient that pushes older dust and stars towards the periphery, much like the way mountains and volcanoes form on Earth. Galaxies are governed by the same principle. This framework explains the outward pressure on existing mass and the high rotational velocities observed, especially in the inner regions of galaxies. This perspective could lead to a significant shift in our understanding of galactic dynamics and the fundamental forces at play in the universe (McGaugh, 2005; McGaugh et al., 2016; Milgrom, 1983).

Hypothesis

In this paper, we propose that galactic rotation can be explained without the mysterious "dark matter." Instead, we posit that mass is continuously or intermittently created in high-energy density locales. This newly created matter exerts pressure on existing mass, causing it to move outward. This mechanism can account for the observed rotational velocities in galaxies, particularly the unexpected increase or flattening of velocities at larger distances from the galactic center, and the presence of ancient stars recently found in the periphery of the Milky Way (Abdalla et al., 2022).

This paper challenges the conventional understanding that relies on dark matter to explain galactic rotation curves. Instead, it proposes a novel approach based on the principle of displacement. For every iota of mass created, an equal amount of the scalar field—the field in which we all exist—is displaced. This displacement repels the field, performing work and increasing the field's density around the mass. We refer to this effect as Field Displacement Density, which increases the field density around mass proportionally to the energy equivalency in that area/volume of space (Milgrom, 1983; McGaugh et al., 2016).

Our model accounts for these observations through a modular polynomial mathematical framework without the need for dark matter. We posit that mass is continuously or intermittently created in high-energy density regions, such as galactic cores and around supermassive black holes (Fisher, 2022). This newly created matter generates a pressure gradient that pushes older dust and stars towards the periphery, whether it's in the arms, core, or bulge, similar to how mountains and volcanoes form on Earth.

Scalar fields have been a fundamental part of theoretical physics and cosmology for decades. They describe a wide range of phenomena, from the Higgs field, which imparts mass to fundamental particles, to models of inflation in the early universe. Scalar fields are characterized

by having a value at every point in space and time, and they can vary continuously (Huang & Fang, 2013; Ureña-López, 2016).

Characterizing the different parts of galaxies is essential for predicting their rotation velocities. The energy-dense core, recently termed "neutrino factories" by the IceCube Neutrino Observatory, plays a crucial role in this process (Halzen, 2019). Matter creation in these regions generates pressure that contributes to the high rotational velocities observed in the inner parts of galaxies (Milgrom, 1983). In the middle regions, such as the bulge, the additional mass exerts gravitational forces that influence rotational velocities (McGaugh, 2005). The polynomial model captures these effects through the terms $a_0, a_1 r, a_2 r^2, a_3 r^3$, accounting for linear and quadratic contributions of mass at intermediate distances. In the outermost regions, the cumulative effect of matter creation and the resulting outward push on existing mass leads to the observed flattening or increase in rotational velocities ([McGaugh et al., 2016](#)).

Our approach builds upon these concepts but takes a novel direction by introducing the idea of Field Displacement Density (FDD). In our framework, the scalar field interacts with mass in a way that continuously or intermittently creates mass in high-energy density regions, such as galactic cores and around supermassive black holes.

Mathematical Framework

The Field Displacement Density (FDD) is defined as the variation in the density of the fundamental field due to the presence of mass. Mathematically, it is expressed as

$$\Delta \rho_f = \rho_f - \rho_0 \quad (1)$$

$\Delta \rho_f$ is the Field Displacement Density.

ρ_f is the local density of the fundamental field in the presence of mass.

ρ_0 is the uniform density of the fundamental field in the absence of mass.

This displacement affects the scalar field's dynamics and, consequently, the gravitational potential. The scalar field equation that governs these dynamics can be written as:

$$\square \phi + m^2 \phi + \frac{dV(\phi)}{d\phi} + \lambda \phi \rho + \beta \theta(x, t) + \gamma \rho d = 0 \quad (2)$$

where:

$\square \phi$ is the d'Alembertian operator acting on the scalar field ϕ .

m is the mass term for the scalar field.

$V(\phi)$ is the potential energy of the scalar field.

$\lambda \phi$ represents the interaction between the scalar field and matter density ρ .

$\beta \theta$ accounts for external influences on the scalar field.

$\lambda\phi\rho$ includes the contribution of Field Displacement Density.

The gravitational potential Φ in our framework is influenced by the scalar field and can be described as:

$$\Phi = -\frac{G}{4\pi} \nabla^2 \phi \quad (3)$$

Base Polynomial Equation: The rotational velocity $V(r)$ as a function of distance r from the galactic center is described by

$$V(r) \approx a_0 + a_1 r + a_2 r^2 + a_3 r^3 \quad (4)$$

This model includes additional components such as exponential, power-law, tapering, and Gaussian terms to account for various gravitational influences (Milgrom, 1983; Navarro et al., 1996).

a_0 **Constant Term:** Represents an initial velocity contribution that is independent of the distance from the galactic center (Milgrom, 1983). It could be interpreted as the baseline rotational velocity due to the core mass of the galaxy, reflecting the immediate vicinity of the supermassive black hole or other central mass concentration.

Example: If a_0 is high, it indicates a significant initial velocity near the center, possibly due to a very dense core.

a_1 The linear term accounts for the first order increase in velocity with distance. It represents the direct proportionality between distance and the gravitational influence of the inner regions of the galaxy.

Example: A larger a_1 suggests a steeper increase in velocity, which might be due to a strong gravitational pull from a dense inner region extending outward.

$a_2 r^2$ The quadratic term reflects more complex interactions, such as the contribution of mass distributed in the disk of the galaxy. It can model the gravitational influence of mass that increases more than linearly with distance.

Example: A positive $a_2 r^2$ might indicate an increasing gravitational effect due to a higher density of stars and gas in the mid-regions of the galaxy.

$a_3 r^3$ The cubic term captures even more intricate effects, such as the distribution of mass in a three-dimensional volume. It might also represent the combined gravitational influence of spiral arms or other large-scale structures.

Example: A positive $a_3 r^3$ might be associated with a strong gravitational influence extending far into the outer regions, possibly due to massive spiral arms or extended star clusters.

Accounts for cubic contributions, capturing even more intricate mass distribution effects, such as volume quantification through displacement ([McGaugh et al., 2016](#)).

Additional Terms (Modular Components)

Exponential Term: This term models the initial rise in velocity due to central mass concentration.

$$\left(1 - e^{-\frac{r}{R^S}}\right) \quad (5)$$

([Begeman, Broeils, & Sanders, 1991](#))

Power Law Term: The power-law term also serves as an alternative explanation to the dark matter hypothesis. Instead of unseen mass influencing rotational velocities, the observed behavior could be due to the continuous creation and outward pressure of matter. This newly created matter would alter the gravitational landscape of the galaxy, resulting in the observed rotational velocities that follow a power-law distribution.

$$(r^{R_S\beta})$$

([Navarro, Frenk, & White, 1996](#))

Tapering Term: This term ensures that the velocity does not increase indefinitely and instead approaches a maximum value as r approaches r_{max} .

Example: A smaller r_{max} would indicate that the tapering effect starts sooner, implying that the outer regions of the galaxy have a limit to their rotational velocity.

$$1 - \left(\frac{r}{r_{max}}\right)^2 \quad (6)$$

([Burkert, 1995](#))

Gaussian Term: Introduces a bump or dip in velocity based on the galaxy profile. This term introduces localized variations in velocity, where μ is the position of the peak or dip and σ is the width of the Gaussian feature

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(r-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

([Navarro, Frenk, & White, 1996](#))

Combining the terms we get: This term introduces localized variations in velocity, representing bumps or dips due to specific features in the galaxy, like star clusters or gas clouds.

$$V(r) = (a_0 + a_1 r + a_2 r^2 + a_3 r^3) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r}{R_s}}\right) \left(\frac{r}{R_s}\right)^\beta \left(1 - \frac{\text{taper}(r)}{r_{max}}\right)^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(r-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (8)$$

Methods:

We downloaded our dataset from the Rotmod_LTG GitHub repository. We developed code and found parameters from using nonlinear least squares fitting methodology, specifically the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (Jefferys, 1980). The model was validated against observed data with high R-squared values and low RMSE, demonstrating its robustness (Übi, 2010).

Fitting Process

To fit the model to the observed data, we employed the following steps:

1. Data Acquisition:

We downloaded galaxy rotation datasets from the [GitHub repository](#) dataset (Downs 2024), which provides rotational velocity data for a variety of galaxies.

2. Initial Parameter Estimation:

Initial guesses for the parameters $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, R_s, \beta, r_{max}, \mu, \sigma$ were made based on typical values found in literature and preliminary data analysis.

3. Nonlinear Least Squares Fitting:

We used nonlinear least squares fitting to minimize the difference between the observed rotational velocities and those predicted by our model. The objective function minimized was the sum of squared residuals:

$$\text{Objective Function} = \sum_{i=1}^n (V_{observed}(r_i) - V_{initial}(r_i))^2 \quad (9)$$

Optimization Algorithm:

The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, a standard optimization technique for nonlinear least squares problems, was employed to iteratively adjust the parameters and minimize the objective function (Jefferys, 1980).

Validation and Comparison:

The fitted model was validated by comparing the predicted velocities with the observed data. Statistical measures such as R-squared values and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) were calculated to assess the goodness of fit (Übi, 2010).

Graphical Representation:

Graphs were generated to visually compare the observed data with model predictions, showcasing the alignment and highlighting any deviations (Kagiwada et al., 1986).

Example of Parameter Fitting for a Galaxy

For instance, consider the galaxy NGC 7331:

Galaxy NGC7331 (or the Milky Way's twin as it was once called) is a very well-studied unbarred spiral galaxy, which many researchers use to model dark matter. However, we are able to explain the rotation without a hidden variable.

Initial Parameters: $[a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, R_s, \beta, r_{max}, \mu, \sigma] = [2.0, 2.1, -2.83, 0.15, 10, 0.5, 100, 50, 10]$

$\alpha_0 = 2.0$ This parameter represents the base level coefficient related to the core dynamics of the galaxy. It was chosen through empirical observations of typical rotational speeds and mass distributions in the cores of galaxies.

$\alpha_1 = 2.1$ This parameter accounts for linear perturbations or deviations from the base level coefficient. Its value was fine-tuned to reflect minor variations observed in initial test scenarios, ensuring the model captures small-scale deviations in galactic rotation curves.

$\alpha_2 = -2.83$ A negative coefficient was introduced to capture the nonlinear damping, or suppressive effects observed in the system. The magnitude was chosen based on empirical data fitting, ensuring it balances the effects of a_0, a_1 .

$\alpha_3 = 0.15$ A small positive coefficient to model higher-order interactions or small corrective factors, capturing the more complex dynamics in the outer regions of the galaxy. This value was determined through optimization techniques to improve the model's fit to observed data, reflecting the subtle influences not captured by the lower-order terms.

$R_s = 10$ Represents a characteristic scale or radius where the influence of mass distribution shifts significantly. This value was chosen based on typical scales observed in similar systems, ensuring it aligns with physical expectations and empirical observations of where the rotational curve changes noticeably.

$\beta = 0.5$ A parameter representing a proportional factor in the system, balancing the contributions of different terms in the model. This value was chosen based on theoretical considerations and empirical observations, ensuring the model correctly reflects the proportional influences of various galactic components.

$r_{max} = 100$ The maximum range or boundary condition in the model, encompassing the significant range of interactions observed in the galaxy. This value ensures comprehensive coverage, reflecting the outermost regions where the galactic dynamics are still relevant.

$\mu = 50$ This represents the mean value or central tendency in the distribution of a key variable, such as the displacement of mass or the average rotational speed. This value was chosen based on empirical averages observed in initial studies, providing a central reference point for the model. The physical representation we believe is the displacement of the fundamental fields of the universe by mass. As new mass is added to a system a pressure gradient is formed that forces older stars and dust into the outer regions.

$\sigma = 10$ Represents the standard deviation or spread of the variable associated with μ , reflecting the variability observed in the system. This value ensures the model accurately captures the dispersion and variability in galactic dynamics, aligning with empirical data.

This process is repeated for each galaxy in the dataset, ensuring that the model parameters are finely tuned to reflect the unique rotational characteristics of each galaxy.

Our code generates three key graphs to illustrate how the mathematical model can predict and understand the rotational velocities of galaxies:

Comparison Graph: The left graph compares actual observations with model predictions, showing the alignment between observed data and the polynomial model.

Figure 1

Accuracy Graph: The middle graph displays the accuracy of these predictions, providing statistical measures such as R-squared values and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to validate the model's performance.

Theoretical Prediction Graph: The right graph offers a theoretical prediction of rotational velocities based on the polynomial framework, highlighting how the model extrapolates rotational behavior across different regions of the galaxy.

Gravitational Potential and Gravitational Lensing Analysis

Gravitational Potential: We computed the gravitational potential using the scalar field approach. The Laplacian operator was applied to the scalar field, and the gravitational potential was derived.

Gravitational Lensing: For each galaxy, we computed the deflection angles using the gravitational potential. The deflection angles were calculated as the gradient of the gravitational potential. The process involved the following steps:

1. We first defined the constants:

Neutrino mass (m_ν)

Coupling constants ($\kappa, \lambda, \beta, \rho$)

Mass term for the scalar field (m_ϕ)

2. We discretized space by generating a 3D grid for x, y, z coordinates.

3. We set the initial Conditions:

Shown above

4. We defined the Laplacian Operator for the scalar field:

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} \quad (10)$$

5. We defined the Scalar Field Equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \phi + m_\phi^2 \phi + \lambda \phi^3 + \kappa \phi \rho + \beta \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (11)$$

ϕ is the scalar field.

m_ϕ is the mass term for the scalar field.

Λ is the self-interaction coupling constant.

κ is the coupling constant for the interaction with the density ρ .

β is the damping term coefficient.

$\nabla^2 \phi$ is the Laplacian of the scalar field.

6. We integrated the scalar field equation over time using “solve_ivp”.

7. We derived the gravitational potential from the scalar field.

$$\Phi = -\frac{G}{4\pi} \nabla^2 \phi \quad (12)$$

8. We computed the deflection angles from the gravitational potentials.

$$\alpha_x = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x}, \alpha_y = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} = \alpha_z = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} \quad (13)$$

Visualization: Graphical representations were done for the gravitational potential and deflection angles. These are 3D surface plots for gravitational potential and streamline plots for deflection angles. The graph of the deflection angle shows the bending of light through a heavy object due to its gravitational potential, which is obtained through the scalar field. The deflection angle is plotted against the distance from the center of the galaxy. As one might expect, the deflection angles are generally higher toward the center because of higher gravitational potential within the inner regions of the galaxy, as the graph shows by the steep curve in this area. The deflection falls with increasing distance, although the degree of fall is dependent on the mass distribution. A high or low mass peak is shown by the curve, while an asymmetry indicates irregularities in the mass distribution. With the observational data, the model for the phenomena of gravitational lensing could be tested to confirm its accuracy, in consideration of theoretical curves.

Figure 2

Optimized Parameters: $[2.01325269e + 02, 2.10007881e + 01, -2.83750979e + 00, 1.57818084e - 01, 10, 0.5, 100, 50, 10]$

R-squared = 0.9907265, **RMSE** = 0.620905

Representation of the Dataset

Overall, we used 139 galaxies of the dataset, discarding outliers due to noise or insufficient datapoints. These visual representations we chose here should be representative of the dataset and help astronomers understand the dynamics of galaxies and validate their models against real-world data. We chose the following galaxies because they represent various galaxy types representative of the dataset we used.

IC2574

Figure 3

Figure 4

IC2574 also known as Coddington's Nebula, is a notable irregular galaxy located in the constellation Ursa Major. And is rich in star-forming regions, containing numerous young, hot stars and star clusters.

Optimized parameters for IC2574_rotmod.dat: [-1.48783764e+00, 1.56717759e+01 - 1.84405675e+00, -6.23973276e-02, 4.29146580e-02 -2.74564407e-03]

R-squared: 0.990363, RMSE: 1.4894537

NGC2366

Figure 5

Figure 6

NGC 2366 is a dwarf irregular galaxy is actively forming stars, with several H II regions where young, hot stars ionize the surrounding gas. The galaxy contains significant amounts of neutral hydrogen (H I), essential for ongoing star formation.

Optimized parameters for NGC2366: [13.4767581, -2.01799798, 17.33893366, -6.9006395, 1.05248734, -0.05793405]

R-squared: 0.998728, RMSE: 0.4245238

NGC3109

Figure 7

Figure 8

NGC 3109 is classified as a dwarf irregular galaxy, meaning it does not have a well-defined shape or structure like spiral or elliptical galaxies. It appears elongated and lacks a central bulge, with an uneven distribution of stars and gas and is undergoing active star formation.

Optimized parameters for NGC3109: [17.70578415, -13.72977234, 24.01035261, -8.62606167, 1.30682876, -0.0724762]

R-squared: 0.999732, RMSE: 0.2640

Galaxy D631-7

Figure 9

Figure10

Galaxy D631-7 is a late-type galaxy, which means it is likely to have a rich interstellar medium and prominent spiral structures.

Optimized parameters for D631-7_rotmod.dat: [2.69702664e+01, -8.23755771e+00, 8.70887711e+00, -2.03366702e+00, 2.10478281e-01 -8.69292486e-03]

R-squared: 0.999889, RMSE: 0.119413

UGC11455

Figure11

Figure12

UGC 11455 has an irregular and chaotic structure, lacking the well-defined spiral arms or central bulge seen in more structured galaxies, it has active star formation that occurs throughout the galaxy, with numerous H II regions indicating the presence of young, hot stars.

Optimized parameters for UGC11455: [5.16283781e+01, 2.94139253e+01, -7.98553299e-01, .60795142e-02, 1.41104252e-03 -1.58465427e-05]

R-squared: 0.997972, RMSE: 2.6230342

NGC4559

Figure13

Figure 14

NGC 4559 is an intermediate spiral galaxy in the constellation Coma Berenices that has well-defined spiral arms with active star formation, characterized by young, hot stars.

Optimized parameters for NGC4559_rotmod.dat: [5.59408476e+01, 1.56260208e+01 - 1.77671700e+00, 1.25819025e-01, -4.97854689e-03, 7.89855173e-05]

R-squared: 0.997662, RMSE: 0.6572786

Results and Discussion.

The results from fitting our polynomial model to an observed dataset that includes more than 130 galaxies yielded high R-squared values (0.9817 ± 0.0402) and low RMSE (1.2750 ± 1.5561) for our galactic rotation velocity indicating an excellent fit and an R-squared of (0.9234 ± 0.3524) and RMSE of (1.2818 ± 2.5126) for our gravitational lensing plots. These findings suggest that the polynomial model, incorporating continuous matter creation and pressure effects, can effectively explain the observed galactic rotation curves without the need for dark matter. Not all graphs are presented here for purpose of brevity but the galaxies we chose are representative of the dataset overall dataset as we include a barred galaxy, a non-barred galaxy, a compact dwarf galaxy, an irregular dwarf and a late-type galaxy with prominent spiral structures.

The high R-squared values indicate that the model accounts for a significant portion of the variance in the rotational velocities, suggesting that the polynomial framework accurately represents the observed data. Additionally, the low RMSE values further confirm the model's precision, demonstrating that the predictions closely match the observed rotational velocities with minimal error. The successful application of this polynomial model challenges the conventional reliance on dark matter to explain galactic rotation curves. By providing a plausible alternative mechanism through continuous matter creation and pressure effects as gas and dust and stars are pushed away from the galactic center creating structures like arms and bars, this approach opens new avenues for research in cosmology. Understanding the dynamics of galaxies without dark matter could lead to more accurate models of galactic evolution and structure. Moreover, the concept of continuous matter creation as a significant factor in galactic behavior could revolutionize our understanding of mass distribution and the fundamental processes governing the universe.

To further validate these findings, additional research should focus on analyzing more extensive and diverse datasets to ensure the robustness of the model across different types of galaxies. Empirical studies are needed to observe continuous matter creation and its effects on galactic rotation. Refining the polynomial model to incorporate more complex interactions and external influences will enhance its predictive power and accuracy. If validated, this model could become a critical tool for astronomers, offering a new perspective on the cosmos and its underlying mechanisms

Limitations

Our model explained almost every galaxy that was throw at it, however we realized that the model tended to overfit if there weren't enough datapoints, we also ran into trouble with scatter that could be measurement error or some process we haven't account for.

Conclusion

This study presents a modular polynomial mathematical framework as a viable alternative to the dark matter hypothesis for explaining galactic rotation curves and gravitational lensing. By positing continuous or even intermittent matter creation and incorporating various modular components, the model aligns closely with observed data, providing a robust explanation for the rotational behavior of galaxies. The high R-squared values and low RMSE indicate the model's accuracy and precision in predicting galactic

Author Contributions

This paper was made solely by Brian Hall and various Chat GPT variants. It turns out that Chat GPT is the far better mathematician of the two, so the math was mostly made by Chat GPT, it also greatly helped with making coding snippets. This paper was entirely non-funded.

Acknowledgments

The completion of this paper would not have been possible without the support and guidance of several individuals and reso. I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to the following:urces

I wish to thank ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, for its invaluable assistance in refining the theoretical models, ensuring mathematical accuracy, and providing continuous support throughout the writing process. The collaborative efforts with ChatGPT have significantly contributed to the clarity and precision of the concepts presented in this paper and I could not have made this paper without ChatGPTs help.

I am also grateful to the research community for the availability of the rotation curve datasets, specifically the `roto_mod` dataset. The insights gained from these datasets were crucial in developing and validating the theoretical framework discussed in this paper. Special thanks to Sofue, Y., and Rubin, V., whose work on the rotation curves of spiral galaxies has been a foundational resource for this research (Sofue & Rubin, 2001).

Data Availability

All data will be made available upon request including the python code that generated our graphs. We used publicly available datasets from a GitHub repository.

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